

OGS AUDIT

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1. AUDIT SUMMARY

As of July 18, 2025, a total of **353,348 synthetic profile (Sprof) files** were identified via the Coriolis GDAC for the global ocean and are listed in a single file named *argo_synthetic-profile_index.txt*. Of these, **25,358** are located in the **Mediterranean Sea**, which corresponds to more than 7%.

2. PURPOSE

The main objective of this audit is to provide data producers and/or operational centers with a prototype shared document describing how OGS operational biogeochemical (BGC) modellers use BGC-Argo data. Furthermore, it aims (i) to present and discuss our methods for the use of BGC-Argo data, and to (ii) to foster a two-way communication process, enhance collaboration, and improve the evaluation of BGC-Argo profiles.

The OGS goal with respect to BGC-Argo is to obtain a robust dataset for operational oceanography purposes, such as model validation and data assimilation. To achieve this, several quality checks have been developed, which are described in more detail in Section 5.

3. OGS quality-control ACTIONS

Figure 3.1 shows the list of quality-control actions performed by OGS.

Fig. 3.1. Flowchart of the OGS quality control (QC) procedure used to generate (i) a validation dataset (Coriolis GDAC) and (ii) a dataset for data assimilation (Assimilated Dataset). The arrows in the central section illustrate the conceptual framework of the QC process, while the table on the right reports the detailed QC steps and criteria.

4. RATIONALE

This audit reflects the discussion held at the 25th Argo Data Management Team Meeting (Trieste, 21-25 October 2024), during which we committed to provide information on how OGS process and handle BGC-Argo data.

5. LIST OF QUALITY CHECK

QCs can be broadly divided into:

- [5a. Variable-independent QC](#)
- [5b. Variable-dependent QC](#)
- [5c. Pre-Data Assimilation QC](#)

5a. Variable-independent QC: Detection of suitable Profiles in the Mediterranean Sea

Methods

Considering data available from 1-1-2013 to 18-07-2025 (last visit on 18-07-2025), from the 353,348 synthetic profiles (Sprof) listed in the argo_synthetic-profile_index.txt file (available on the Coriolis FTP server), OGS first apply automatic filters to exclude files that are not relevant for the specific regions of the Mediterranean Sea.

To do this, we initially work on the argo_synthetic-profile_index.txt file, discarding all profiles that do not contain latitude, longitude, and date information (missing data).

After this step, we spatially filter the data to retain only profiles located in the Mediterranean Sea and then apply an additional filter to select only the ascending profiles.

Results

The downloaded dataset consists of the 353,348 profiles, while the selected ascending profiles for the Mediterranean Sea are 25,358. Below is a summary of the filters applied, with the number of discarded/accepted profiles in parentheses:

The variable-independent QC and selection of Mediterranean profiles include the following filters:

- Sprof with Lat-lon missing data (discard **3656** Sprof global ocean)
- Remove descending profiles (discard **14608** Sprof global ocean)
- Select Sprof files in the Mediterranean Sea (retained **25,368** Sprof in MedSea)
- Unknown motivation that should be further investigated (10 discarded → 6902902: profiles 467-482 in MedSea)

The complete list of discarded profiles can be provided upon request.

5b. Variable-dependent QCs: Filtering and correction of profiles applied for the Mediterranean Sea

Each variable undergoes specific QCs, although in some cases certain basic steps are common to all variables.

CHLOROPHYLL

Filtering Criteria:

- Profiles of chlorophyll or temperature are discarded if the vertical length of their PRES (pres_chl or pres_T) is fewer than 5 pressure observations (if length(PRES<0))
- Vertical observations are thinned out if that the distance between consecutive pressure points is lower than least 2 m;
- Profiles are discarded if all available observations are located below 200 m.
- Profiles are retained only if their mode is Adjusted or Delayed (AM or DM);
- The quality flag of each observation must be “good,” “probably good,” “value changed,” or “estimated value” (flags 1, 2, 5, 8). Measurements flagged as “bad” or “probably bad” (qc = 3 or 4) are filtered out from the profile.

Correction Criteria:

- Profile shift/offset analysis at depth: if the mean chlorophyll concentration in the 400–600 m layer is > 0 , an offset is calculated and applied to the entire profile so that the corrected profile satisfies $[CHLA]_{avg,400-600m}=0$;
- After the previous check, the negative chlorophyll concentrations are replaced with the background value of 0.005 mg m^{-3} .

Summary Output

A summary table of these checks are provided in the file CHLA_Audit.csv, whose header explains the meaning of each column. Figures showing profiles before and after correction, as well as the discarded profiles, are available upon request.

Wmo	Cycle	Data_Mode	QC_flag	Pres_CHLA	Len_Pres_TEMP	Pres_rarefy	AVG_shift	dumped_file	date	date_update
6901775	234	A	1,5,8	463	ok	231	0.009000	1	2022-01-06	2025-07-27
6902902	402	A	4	463	ok	0	NaN	0	2022-01-02	2025-07-27
6902902	403	A	4	437	ok	0	NaN	0	2022-01-04	2025-07-27
6902902	404	A	4	422	ok	0	NaN	0	2022-01-06	2025-07-27
6902902	405	A	4	493	ok	0	NaN	0	2022-01-08	2025-07-27
6903805	23	A	1,5,8	404	ok	186	0.002486	1	2022-01-01	2025-07-27
6903805	24	A	1,5,8	390	ok	185	0.002663	1	2022-01-06	2025-07-27
7900562	174	A	1,5	299	ok	299	0.010950	1	2022-01-02	2025-07-27
7900562	175	A	1,5	296	ok	296	0.010220	1	2022-01-07	2025-07-27

Fig 5.1. Example of CHLA__QCs_info.csv

OXYGEN

Filtering Criteria:

- Profiles of oxygen or temperature are discarded if the vertical length of their PRES (pres_doxy or pres_T) is less than approximately 10 m (fewer than 5 pressure observations);
- Vertical observations are thinned out so that the distance between consecutive pressure points is at least 2 m;
- A Min–Max test range is applied; measurements outside the range [140, 280] mmol m⁻³ are removed;
- Only Delayed Mode (DM) profiles are retained;
- Adjusted Mode profiles are discarded if the oxygen saturation in the 0–5 m layer (calculated by using the equation of Garcia & Gordon, 1992) differs from the mean dissolved oxygen by more than 10 mmol m⁻³;
- The quality flag of each observation must be “good,” “probably good,” “value changed,” or “estimated value” (flags 1, 2, 5, 8). Measurements flagged as “bad” or “probably bad” (qc = 3 or 4) are filtered out from the profile.

Correction Criteria:

Oxygen profiles and data are corrected when the BGC-Argo oxygen sensor is potentially affected by sensor drift. The conditions required for performing the drift analysis are:

- The float lifetime ≥ 1 year.
- Availability of oxygen data at 600 m and 800 m depth.

If the above conditions are met, the following methodology is applied else profiles undergo to the next check (**Climatological check see below**) :

- Drift is calculated using two non-parametric regression methods (RANSAC and Theil–Sen) at 600 m and 800 m, resulting in four estimates.
- A sign analysis is performed; all four estimates must have the same sign. If not, the sensor is considered not affected by drift.
- The mean of the four values is compared to a threshold of 1 mmol m⁻³ yr⁻¹ (threshold from literature Bushinsky et al. (2016), Bittig et al., (2018a), Maurer

et al. (202)). If the mean is below this threshold, the sensor is considered not affected by drift.

- If a drift is detected, oxygen profiles are corrected by subtracting the drift value at 600 m and linearly reducing it toward zero at the surface to minimize the impact in upper layers (for methodological details, see Amadio et al., 2024).
- The Sprof file is updated with a metadata flag called DRIFT_CODE, indicating the outcome of the analysis:
 - DRIFT_CODE = 0 → the BGC-Argo float is not affected by drift.
 - DRIFT_CODE = -1 → the conditions for trend analysis are not satisfied.
 - DRIFT_CODE = 1 → a drift is detected and corrected.

Wmo	Cycle	Data_Mode	Mission_duration	Theil-Sen	RANSAC	Yearly_Trend	Drift_correction	Drift_code	basin
6903804	22	A	35.0	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	-1.0	lev2
6903805	23	A	47.0	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	-1.0	adr2
6903803	22	A	105.0	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	-1.0	lev1
6903803	23	A	109.0	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	-1.0	lev1
6903802	30	A	139.0	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	-1.0	NaN
6903802	31	A	144.0	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	-1.0	NaN
6903068	41	D	199.0	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	-1.0	nwm
6903068	42	D	204.0	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	-1.0	nwm
6903765	161	A	800.0	12.967472	13.810341	NaN	NaN	-1.0	ion3
6903765	162	A	805.0	12.222807	14.274793	NaN	NaN	-1.0	ion3
6902876	185	A	919.0	-6.858247	-4.875513	-5.447878	-2.163738	1.0	swm2
6902876	186	A	924.0	-7.270556	-5.152424	-5.650503	-2.232071	1.0	swm2
6903266	347	A	986.0	-4.935387	-10.452156	-5.436183	-2.012380	1.0	NaN
6903262	205	A	1020.0	23.884291	25.093761	NaN	NaN	-1.0	NaN
6902875	212	A	1021.0	-0.617697	1.118695	NaN	NaN	-1.0	ion3
6902870	212	A	1021.0	3.069531	-1.078613	NaN	NaN	-1.0	ion2
6903262	206	A	1024.0	23.828141	24.149114	NaN	NaN	-1.0	NaN
6902873	220	A	1029.0	1.295174	-0.029862	NaN	NaN	-1.0	lev1
6902872	264	A	1067.0	8.796105	10.694907	NaN	NaN	-1.0	ion3
6902872	265	A	1072.0	9.027503	10.896055	NaN	NaN	-1.0	ion3
6901774	206	A	1088.0	-0.260951	0.098021	NaN	NaN	-1.0	swm1
6903237	279	A	1090.0	-7.655340	-9.961916	NaN	NaN	-1.0	NaN
6901775	234	A	1091.0	10.975709	12.841705	NaN	NaN	-1.0	ion3

Fig 5.2. Example of DOXY_QCs_info.csv illustrating the drift correction QC columns

Filtering Criteria:

Profiles are discarded based on a climatological consistency check:

- Oxygen concentration is evaluated at 600 m depth.
- The difference between the measured oxygen value and a climatological reference (e.g., EMODnet; bla bla) at the same depth is calculated.
- Profiles are excluded if this difference exceeds twice the standard deviation of the reference dataset.

Summary Output

A summary table of these checks is provided in the file Doxy_Audit.csv, whose header explains the meaning of each column. Figures showing profiles before and after correction, as well as the discarded profiles, are available upon request.

Wmo	Cycle	basin	Clim_mean	Diff	2*st_dev
6901774	206	swm1	181.96893	-11.206767	15.242246
6901775	234	ion3	197.16876	-7.240250	21.034862
6902870	212	ion2	188.51926	-0.893020	12.722744
6902872	264	ion3	197.16876	-17.950592	21.034862
6902872	265	ion3	197.16876	-17.689000	21.034862
6902873	220	lev1	188.50610	-11.582269	19.875300
6902875	212	ion3	197.16876	-11.668530	21.034862
6902876	185	swm2	175.18611	-1.514588	13.302958
6902876	186	swm2	175.18611	-2.573238	13.302958
6903068	41	nwm	186.52608	-9.135948	21.226374
6903068	42	nwm	186.52608	-10.042686	21.226374
6903237	279	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN
6903262	205	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

Fig 5.3. Example of DOXY__QCs_info.csv illustrating the filtering QC columns.

NITRATE

Filtering Criteria

- Profiles of nitrate or temperature are discarded if the vertical extent (pres_nitrate or pres_T) extent is less than approximately 10 m (fewer than 5 pressure observations);
- Vertical observations are thinned out so that the distance between consecutive pressure points is at least 2 m;
- The quality flag of each observation must be “good,” “probably good,” “value changed,” or “estimated value” (flags 1, 2, 5, 8). Measurements flagged as “bad” or “probably bad” (qc = 3 or 4) are filtered out from the profile;
- Below 50 m measurements with positive nitrate concentrations are retained;
- Profiles are discarded if the deepest valid pressure of the NITRATE profile is shallower than 100 m;
- Only Delayed Mode (DM) profiles are retained;
- Adjusted Mode (AM) profiles with deepest valid pressure less or equal than 600 m, are discarded.

Correction Criteria

For Adjusted Mode profiles with a maximum depth > 600 m, a correction is applied based on a reference climatology calculated MedBGCins at 600 m (add ref):

- A shift is calculated as the difference between the profile values between 600-800 m and the climatology's reference at the same depth layer.
- This shift is applied to the entire profile (linear offset) to align it with the MedBGCins reference.
- The corrected profile, updated QC flags (set to 8), and the applied shift are returned and stored in the metadata.
- Negative nitrate concentrations in the upper 50 m are replaced by a small positive value (0.05 mmol m^{-3});

OGS reconstruct nitrate profiles using a neural network-based model (1-D Predict Profiles Convolutional Neural Network, PPCon, Pietropolli 2024) from sets of temperature, salinity, oxygen, date, latitude, and longitude in BGC-Argo profiles. The PPcon_nitrate profile is flagged as -9999 for quality control and undergoes all nitrate-specific checks.

Summary Output

A summary table of these checks is provided in the file Nitrate_Audit.csv, whose header explains the meaning of each column. Figures showing profiles before and after correction, as well as the discarded profiles, are available upon request

wmo	cycle	Data_Mode	Pres_raw	Pres_rarefy	maxdepth	qc_flag	lenPresT	AM_shift	Count_negative_val
6901772	225	A	75	74	1967.850100	2	ok	performed	0
6902904	233	A	77	75	1963.449951	2	ok	performed	0
6903805	23	A	33	31	996.929993	2	ok	performed	0
6903805	24	A	33	31	986.650024	2	ok	performed	0

Fig 5.4. Example of NITRATE_QCs_info.csv

5c. Data Assimilation QCs: Filtering of profiles applied for the Mediterranean Sea.

To assimilate BGC-Argo data in the OGS' operational BGC model of the Mediterranean Sea, additional quality checks are applied. Profiles may be excluded during data assimilation if the innovation (the difference between the model state prior to assimilation and the BGC-Argo observations) exceeds predefined thresholds. These exclusions are designed to avoid corrections that could trigger unstable dynamics in the model after assimilation.

- Chlorophyll: threshold of 2 mg m^{-3} in the 0–200 m layer.
- Oxygen: thresholds of 30 mmol m^{-3} (0–150 m) and 50 mmol m^{-3} (150–600 m).
- Nitrate: thresholds of 2 mmol m^{-3} (0–50 m) and 3 mmol m^{-3} (250–600 m).

Exceeding values must be present in at least five vertical levels within the specified layer for all variables.

Additional nitrate check: profiles with nitrate concentrations $> 3 \text{ mmol m}^{-3}$ in the 0–15 m surface layer are not assimilated.

Summary Output

A summary table of these statistics is provided. Figures showing profiles before and after the data assimilation and BGC-Argo can be done upon request.

WMO	Basin	AVG_misfit_0-50m	Excluded_0-50m	AVG_misfit_250-600m	Depth_Exclusion	Excluded_250-600m	Excluded_0-15m	INSITU
6901772	ion2	2.66	1.0	NaN	NaN	0.0	1.0	1.0
6903068	nwm	NaN	0.0	NaN	NaN	0.0	1.0	0.0
6903068	nwm	NaN	0.0	NaN	NaN	0.0	1.0	0.0
6903068	nwm	NaN	0.0	NaN	NaN	0.0	1.0	0.0
6903263	adr1	1.20	1.0	NaN	NaN	0.0	1.0	0.0
6901772	ion2	5.60	1.0	2.1	262.653229	1.0	1.0	1.0

Fig 5.4. Example of Pre_DA_QCs_info.csv